

COVERING THE NEEDS OF MIXED-ABILITY CLASS

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ANNOTATION

Mixed-ability classrooms have been identified as one of the most significant detriments to students studying at schools. There is rising worry about the effects of mixed-ability courses, prompting the need for a research to identify alternatives. This study includes five female EFL teachers who work at schools, and their responses were acquired through interview. The questionnaires addressed this issue on several levels, including teaching and learning, materials, motivation, and class management procedures.

Keywords: *Mixed-ability classes, strategies, English first language (EFL), classroom.*

1. Introduction

The mixed-ability class is one of the many issues that teachers face nowadays. A mixed-ability classroom, according to Chapman and King (2003), is made up of students with varying degrees of learning abilities, interests, and talents. EFL teachers have come to recognize this as one of the most important factors that defines the degree of instruction and knowledge of what the students go through in the long run. While each learner has their own unique way of learning English, as well as distinct linguistic knowledge and learning pace, there appears to be an overarching necessity for the instructor to use approaches that engage all pupils in the same measure. This is especially true when the instructor is unsure about which students to focus on. Should they focus on the advanced students while ignoring the lesser ones? The converse

would be detrimental to advanced learners, since they would not be able to participate to their full ability. Following this scenario, this study seeks to investigate the obstacles of mixed-ability courses as well as the techniques used by EFL teachers to solve these issues.

2. Literature review

Mixed-ability classes are those in which students have a wide variety of achievement and learning levels. Students in these classrooms have distinct skills and weaknesses, as well as varied methods to learning. Scholars have described this topic in a variety of ways, drawing on distinct insights garnered from various learning situations. Ansari (2013), for example, defines a mixed-ability class as one that includes not only learners of varying abilities, but also individuals with a diverse set of preferences and learning styles. They can also be referred to as a subset of students based on their grammatical knowledge, fluency and accuracy, vocabulary size, receptive and productive capabilities (Valentic, 2005).

Notably, several elements, such as attitude, motivation, and self-discipline, might differ from one student to the next (Lightbown & Spada, 2006). This makes it difficult for teachers to successfully arrange their lessons in order to ensure that all of their students benefit from the session. This is especially difficult for language instructors who lack the necessary skills and teaching approaches to deal with mixed-ability classes (Ansari, 2013). Most educational institutions have addressed this issue by splitting courses based on age. However, these classifications are still multileveled because individual abilities are still considered random.

However, there are benefits to teaching in mixed-ability courses that are typically obscured by the problems. These classrooms provide engaging learning environments since they are made up of a broad set of talents, attitudes, and perspectives. Most significantly, the interactions in these programs allow students to be more creative and imaginative by learning from one another's unique strengths. The problems faced by language teachers in mixed-ability classrooms, on the other hand,

are frequently numerous and usually lead to frustration on their side since they are unable to create a fruitful learning and teaching environment for their pupils.

Teachers are also confronted with a scarcity of training programs and practices to prepare them for such workplace conditions. These tactics have been proposed as critical and helpful in ensuring student success in their learning experiences. The truth is that most instructors lack professional development, preparation time, and the ability to regularly use differentiation (Loiacono & Allen, 2008). Continuous training for instructors in mixed-ability classrooms is required to effectively manage the challenges of their varied pupils (Butterworth, 2010).

Most classrooms have a high number of students, and it is the teacher's obligation to keep the pupils under control and to deliver the lesson successfully. Because the burden for meeting the particular needs of each student falls solely on the shoulders of a single teacher, it has become a time-consuming process. Because each student has a distinct degree of knowledge, it has become tough to implement their lesson plans in a mixed-ability class (Northcote 2006).

3. Methodology.

The aim of this article is analyzing of mixed ability classes and teachers' different methods to cover their needs . For doing this, interview method is used and five teachers are selected and participated.

Participants.

N	Participants	Work place	Experience	What classes they teach	Level of the teacher
1.	O'ktamova Asila	29 th Fergana region	2 year	1 st , 2 nd , 9 th , 11 th	C1
2.	Muqimxo'jayeva Xushnoza	16 th Fergana region	2 year	7 th	C1
3.	Olimjonova To'lganoy	51 st Fergana region	2 year	1 st , 2 nd	B2
4.	Axmedova Zarnigor	9 th Fergana region	2 year	1 st , 2 nd	C1
5.	Shahnoza Fozilova	18 th Fergana region	2 year	1 st	C1

Research method: Interview. An interview is an organized conversation in which one person asks questions and the other responds. The term "interview" is commonly used to refer to a one-on-one talk between an interviewer and an interviewee.

When: 19th of October **Where:** At university **How:** Face to face

Data collecting tool: Interview.

Interview questions:

1. Describe your approach to teaching vocabulary to learners with different proficiency levels.
2. Share an example of how you give instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners in your classroom.
3. Tell me about how you adapt your teaching style or materials to meet the needs of a specific student.

4. Data analysis and discussion.

Almost all of my interviewees had similar responses. Four of my respondents answered to my first question by saying that they utilize visuals and have pupils repeat after them while teaching vocabulary. They think that it is the best way both to teach vocabulary and cover all the needs of students of mixed ability classes. However, X.M preferred the collaborative approach, believing that if we force pupils to work in groups or with peers, they will learn new language more quickly. Also she added that working collaboratively not only helps to learn vocabulary better but also it can improve students' social skills and they can easily integrate with each other.

In response to the second question, A.O' , Sh.F , X.M like to provide a variety of resources and assignments while providing directions in order to meet the requirements of varied learners in the classroom. They claimed that they take their level, interest, learning style and age into account while choosing materials. Z.A , T.O conduct new topics by describing them broadly, and if passive students do not understand the concept, they deal with them personally. As they teach 2 grade students they work with students' parents because young students cannot understand the

pressure and in this situation co-working of teacher and parents will be the best solution.

They gave varied answers to the third interview question. M.X employs exercises for tactile learners and realias. She mentioned that if teacher do not fulfill the needs of students, students will not be engaged in lesson. And A.Z. and F.SH employ visual aids based on the pupils' learning styles as they have more visual learners in their class.. However, O'.A and O.T make supplementary activities more difficult for greater levels, but the goal is the same; the only difference is the level. In that case, both upper and lower level of students will not get bored during the lesson and they will get immersed in class.

5. Conclusion.

According to the findings of this study, the mixed-ability kids found in nearly all schools and classes face their teachers with significant challenges in teaching effectively. When students publish unfavorable unanticipated findings, teachers are said to feel out of touch with them or out of control. These issues necessitate the use of efficient management approaches by the teachers in order to handle them. This can be accomplished by employing various ways in order to test various strategies and choose the most effective ones.

Aside from implementing these management strategies, instructors must emphasize the good features of the classes. Due to the intricacies involved, teaching these classes can be difficult, yet mixed-ability classes are noted for their unique capabilities. Following that, the instructors should concentrate more on these strengths. A good way to achieve this is to create specialized assignments for each level in order to keep pupils involved and so boost their learning ability.

Furthermore, teachers who have a positive attitude toward student ability diversity are more successful when teaching mixed-ability classes. Planning particular tasks for the students' various levels of ability will guarantee that all learners are involved in the learning process and at personal levels, ensuring efficiency and success in the teaching of mixed-ability classrooms.

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